

Altitudinal variation of goat blood biochemical and antioxidant parameters in a sub-tropical region of India

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Abstract

Goat is the most important source of income for the rural populace. Goat health and production depends upon environmental factors. The present study aims to understand the influence of different altitudes on the morphology, biochemical, and antioxidant parameters changes in goats. The rectal temperature (RT), body length (BL), body height (BH), tail length (TL), horn length (HL), ear length (EL), and head width (HW) were measured as the morpho-physiological parameters. Glucose, total protein, albumin, triglyceride, creatinine, urea, uric acid, alanine aminotransferase, and aspartate aminotransferase were analyzed for biochemical parameters. Whereas, FRAP, DPPH, and ABTS were measured as the antioxidant parameters. Results showed that significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher BL, BH, and significantly lower HL. All the biochemical parameters were within the range of normal levels, as suggested by a different researcher. After statistical analysis, it has been found that there was no significant variation between the two locations except the glucose level. It has been found that goat off the Indora region; the low altitude area has a significant ($p < 0.05$) higher glucose level than the Chamba region, a higher altitude region. However, there were no significant changes in the antioxidant parameters between the two altitudes. From this result, it might be concluded that altitude has effects on goat morphology. There was no altitudinal effect on the biochemical and antioxidant parameters of the goat.

Keywords: ABTS; Altitude; DPPH; FRAP; Goat; Himachal Pradesh

Goat is a ubiquitous domestic animal in all the areas of the high-altitude regions, including upper Himachal like Chamba, Kullu, Bilaspur. Instead of this, goat rearing has a significant impact on socio-economy development in lower Himachal, like in Kangra district, Indora. Goat is

the high nutritional sources by yielding chevon. It is also a source of wool-like pashmina goat produce a large quantity of this wool in the high-altitude region like Leh-Ladakh of J&K, and an upper area of Himachal Pradesh. This high-altitude region is mainly cut-off from the rest of the world due to the extreme climatic condition, which is characterized by the high snowfall, shallow temperature, and high wind velocity for at least nine months. During this period, the local population is intimately dependent upon the livestock population, mainly on the goat for the milk, chevon, and wool. Goat rearing is very economically supportive for low-income farmers in this region. This is the only source of income

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Figure 1: Site of the goat blood sample collection at Bharmour and Indora, Himachal Pradesh prepared by Google 3D Earth Software

and daily livelihood for the local populace. According to 19th livestock censuses (Dept. Dept of Animal Husbandry Dairying & Fisheries 2012) in Chamba and Kangra has high numbers of goats, i.e., 204511 and 202694, respectively. Goats are an essential source of proteins as meat, and many useful properties present in the milk of goat (Giri et al. 2019; Kumar et al. 2019; Khushboo et al. 2020). But, proper rearing of the goat is not maintained in this region. Mostly, the housing system of this area for goat rearing is an open system, and sometimes the housing system has a closed and congested system (Giri et al. 2019). At the lower altitude region, the scenario is different. For increasing the quality and quantity of products from goat, it is necessary to understand solves the problems which come due to various environmental factors (Bharti et al. 2017). Due to different altitudes and different environmental conditions, different types of vegetation develop, which also show the effects on the health conditions of local animals. In this study, the selected study areas are from two different altitudes. One area belongs to the Chamba district of Himachal Pradesh, is the area of high altitude. Another study area belongs from

the Indora tehsil of lower Kangra district, Himachal Pradesh, which is characterized by a slightly low altitude region than the Chamba district. Due to altitude dependent variation in temperature, environmental and climatic factors, the physiology of goat may be altered. Still, in these aspects, no study has been done yet. In this context, this study has been done to evaluate the morphological, biochemical, and antioxidant properties in the goat population of the different altitudes of Himachal Pradesh, a subtropical region.

This study was executed in two different locations with different altitudes. One sampling location was in Garola village, tehsil Bharmour, district Chamba, (H.P.), India (Figure 1). It is situated at an altitude of 6000 ft. The second location was the Indora village, tehsil Indora, District Kangra (H.P.), India (Figure 1).

Total fifteen (10 from Chamba and 5 from Indora) clinically healthy goats (average age was 2-3 yrs) were selected for blood sample collections (Figure 2) in December 2018. After the centrifugation of blood samples, serum and plasma samples were placed in the deep freezer

Figure 2: Blood sample collection from goat

Figure 3: Measurement of goat morphological parameters

for preservation until further experimental analysis. After the blood sample collection, by using the measuring tape, all the physical parameters (Body Length, Body Height, Tail Length, Horn Length, Ear Length, and Head Width) were measured and a digital thermometer was used for measurement of rectal temperature (Figure 3).

For the biochemical parameters like glucose (mg/dl), total protein (TP - mg/dl), albumin (ALB - g/dl), triglyceride (TG - mg/dl), creatinine (CRT - mg/dl), Urea (mg/dl), uric acid (UA - mg/dl), alanine aminotransferase (ALT -U/l), and aspartate aminotransferase (AST - U/l) were analyzed by serum semi-auto analyzer (pace^{vet}28 of Ocean Medical Technologies) (Giri 2018).

For antioxidant parameter analysis, DPPH (Abe et al. 2000), FRAP (Benzie and Strain 1996), and ABTS (Turoli et al. 2004) performed for antioxidant parameters evaluated in plasma samples. To determine the statistical significance between the two altitudes, all the data set of morphological, biochemical, and antioxidant parameters has executed by the ‘t’-test by using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) 24.0 IBM version software. The level of significance determined at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table 1. Difference between different morphological parameters of goat from two different altitudes

Sr. No.	Parameters	Abbreviation	Unit	Indora (Mean ± SEM)	Chamba (Mean ± SEM)
1.	Rectal Temperature	RT	°C	52.10 ± 0.11	52.71 ± 0.29
2.	Body Length	BL	Inch	24.25 ± 1.11	23.15 ± 0.77*
3.	Body Height	BH	Inch	29.25 ± 0.25	25.65 ± 1.06*
4.	Tail Length	TL	Inch	8.75 ± 0.48	8.90 ± 0.87
5.	Horn Length	HL	Inch	2.50 ± 0.94	4.90 ± 0.61*
6.	Ear Length	EL	Inch	7.63 ± 0.24	7.10 ± 0.31
7.	Head Width	HW	Inch	4.25 ± 0.25	4.50 ± 0.22

Values are presented as mean ± SEM and *indicate significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference between the goat morphology of Indora and Chamba within the row.

Location	Glucose (mg/dl)	TP (mg/dl)	ALB (g/dl)	TG (mg/dl)	CRT (mg/dl)	Urea (mg/dl)	UA (mg/dl)	ALT (U/l)	AST (U/l)
Chamba	34.88 ±3.69	64.72 ±5.28	2.38 ±0.08	33.44 ±3.87	1.28 ±0.09	29.49 ±4.38	0.20 ±0.07	20.85 ±1.20	87.23 ±1.99
Indora	58.06 ±6.22*	63.30 ±4.09	2.60 ±0.11	28.24 ±4.48	1.35 ±0.06	33.99 ±6.45	0.10 ±0.04	21.75 ±3.42	67.00 ±9.45
Reference Level	49 - 91 ^a	63 - 85 ^b	2.8 - 4.3 ^b	2.88 - 28.83 ^b	0.6-1.6 ^d	8 - 26 ^c	-----	20 - 360 ^a	80 - 170 ^a

Values are mean± std. deviation (n=3); for each column, different lowercase letter significantly differ at $p \leq 0.05$ using Tukey's HSD. ^a(Kiran et al. 2012), ^b(Daramola, Adeloye, and Saladoye 2004); ^c(Babeker and Elamansaury 2013); ^d(Jackson and Cockcroft 2007)

Parameters	Unit	Chamba	Indora
ABTS	µmol/L	51.92±0.96	48.44±3.14
FRAP	mg TE/100 cm ³	1.69±0.17	1.41±0.02
DPPH	%	46.02±15.06	47.18±26.77

The descriptive statistics showed that in Indora region the mean value of RT was 52.10±0.11°C, BL was 24.25±1.11 inch, BH was 29.25±0.25 inch, TL was 8.75±0.48 inch, HL was 2.50±0.94 inch, EL was 7.63±0.24 inch, and HW was 4.25±0.25 inch (Table 1). BL and BH of goat were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the Chamba region than the Indora region goat. HL was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower in the Chamba region than the Indora region (Table 1). Body size is the most important parameter among all other morphological parameters to determine the effects of altitude on animals. In our study, it was found that significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher body length, body height, and significantly lower horn length. Larger body size of animals has a lower metabolic rate, which indirectly reduces the heat gain. At higher altitudes, lower heat gain facilitates the survivability of animals at higher altitudes (Turoli et al. 2004; Cain et al. 2006).

All the biochemical parameters were within the range of normal levels, as suggested by a different researcher. After statistical analysis, it has been found that there was no

significant variation between the two locations except the glucose level (Table 2). It has been found that goat off the Indora region; the low altitude area has a significant ($p < 0.05$) higher glucose level than the Chamba region, a higher altitude region (Table 2). Therefore, this might be due to the attenuation of those factors which are responsible for the insulin production in high altitude region (Malcolm et al. 2017).

The results for the ABTS, FRAP, and DPPH performed in Independent 't'-test on plasma sample of goat reflected the variations in values. Still, none of these variables were significant ($p > 0.05$). ABTS and FRAP levels in the serum sample of goats of Chamba in significantly higher than the goats of Indora (Table 3). In another case, the DPPH level of the Chamba goat was insignificantly ($p > 0.05$) lower than the Indora goats (Table 3). So, this result indicated that there was no variation of oxidative stress due to the different altitudes. In the biochemical results, the level of ALT, AST, UA was within the normal range. Like ALT, AST level was at a normal level, so the liver has no stress (Giri et al. 2019; Kumar

et al. 2019; Giri et al. 2017). It was also indicated that due to altitudinal variation, there were no alterations in physio-biochemical parameters.

The present study was designed to determine the effects of altitude on goat morphology, biochemical, and antioxidant parameters. The results showed a higher altitude region has a higher body shape of a goat than the low altitude region. There was no altitudinal effect on the biochemical and antioxidant parameters.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

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